

UMERC+METS 2024 Abstract

Title: Can Cambered Blades Help Cross-Flow Turbine Performance? Part II: Computational Investigation of Unsteady Flow Physics

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Proposed Submission Section: Tidal

Device or component design, analysis, simulation, and optimization

Laboratory and open-water experimental testing of devices or components

Abstract: The flow over cross-flow turbines is complex to analyze due to the orientation of the rotation axis, which causes dynamic stall and the periodic switching of pressure and suction sides. Most previous research has been focused on the use of symmetrical airfoils because of these periodic phenomena. Unlike axial-flow turbines, flow is curvilinear relative to the rotating airfoil of a cross-flow turbine, so an equivalent airfoil in rectilinear flow will have a virtual camber added to it. It is therefore not yet well-understood how airfoil shape influences turbine performance, especially in conjunction with other factors such as the number of blades, chord-to-radius ratio and Reynolds number. Experimental results have shown that the direction of camber affects different parts of the cycle: concave-out camber improves upstream performance but reduces downstream performance, while concave-in camber does the opposite. This project aims to understand the unsteady flow physics behind these changes in performance, and explore the effects of turbine geometry and its relation to virtual camber.

Computational fluid dynamics simulations are used to analyze the performance of turbines with cambered blades. A baseline NACA 0018 airfoil is cambered in both the inward and outward direction by up to 3%. To do this, mesh points near the airfoil are morphed accordingly to maintain topological consistency between meshes. A two-dimensional incompressible Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes model is implemented using OpenFOAM to simulate the turbine, and results are validated against experimental performance and particle image velocimetry data. Three-dimensional large-eddy simulation models are also tested to analyze their accuracy in comparison to the two-dimensional model and experimental results. The validated simulation results are then used to study the near-blade flow structures of the cambered airfoils, such as the timing of vortex shedding, which is difficult to capture experimentally.

The use of numerical methods allows for a more comprehensive exploration of the parameter space. Variations in geometry, such as chord-to-radius ratio and maximum camber location, are analyzed in the context of varying camber, since these parameters have a strong relation to virtual camber. Tip speed ratio and Reynolds number are also evaluated. The results of this project may be used to improve the geometry of cross-flow turbines for optimal performance and control strategies.

Bio: Caelan Consing is a Masters student in the Mechanical Engineering department at the University of Wisconsin-Madison under the guidance of Jennifer Franck. He is interested in the applications of computational fluid dynamics, particularly in renewable energy. His research is focused on cross-flow turbines and the optimization of their geometry and configuration. Caelan's interest in the field started in the University of the Philippines, where his undergraduate thesis investigated the effects of leading-edge tubercles on axial turbines. He received his B.S. in Mechanical Engineering and was awarded the Vicente T. Paterno Award for Excellence in Mechanical Engineering in August 2023, before starting his research assistantship at UW-Madison.